

MODELING OF MATHEMATICAL PHYSICS EQUATIONS

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ABSTRACT Many processes in modern physics are explained by solving the equations of mathematical physics. These equations are nonlinear differential equations that cannot always be solved analytically. In this work, we solved the equations of mathematical physics using the software package "wolfram mathematica" and analyzed the results.

Keywords: Modeling, hyperbolic equation, parabolic equation, elliptic equation, NDSolve, Plot, Manipulate.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main tasks of mathematical physics is to determine effective methods of solving partial differential equations [2]. For two-dimensional problems, the second-order equation with the partial derivative is generally written as follows:

$$a \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + b \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t \partial x} + c \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + d \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + e \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + fu + g = 0$$

where u is an arbitrary unknown function; a, b, c, d, e, f and g are coefficients of x (coordinate) and t (time) can be a function. In the linear case, this equation is $D = b^2(x, t) - 4a(x, t)c(x, t)$ depending on the sign of the discriminant, it is classified into hyperbolic, parabolic and elliptical types as follows:

- $D > 0$ is an equation of hyperbolic type
- $D = 0$ is a parabolic equation
- $D < 0$ is an equation of elliptic type

In physics, the following problems described by equations of this type can be listed: the problem of wave propagation, the problem of heat propagation, the problem of diffusion, the mass of electrostatics (Laplace, Poisson's equation).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Nowadays, modern science cannot be imagined without computers. In particular, scientists are using various computer programs to solve mathematical physics equations. Including E.N. Trofimets and V.Ya. We can see that Trophimets widely used the Mathcad programming package in solving problems related to aerospace [1]. Programming packages such as Matlab, Maple, Wolfram mathematica, Mathcad are highly capable of solving such problems. In this work, we used "Wolfram mathematica" programming package to numerically solve hyperbolic, parabolic and elliptic type problems.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

To achieve the intended goal, we will consider some problems described by equations corresponding to hyperbolic, parabolic and elliptic types [4]:

1. The problem of transverse vibrations of a string (hyperbolic equation)
2. Heat diffusion problem (parabolic type equation)
3. Laplace equation (elliptic type equation)

The problem of transverse vibration of a string

Let a string of length L be fixed at both ends. The initial velocity of the narrow points is zero and the initial displacement is $\varphi(x)$. Solve the problem of transverse vibrations of this string?

It is known from the course of mathematical physics equations that the problem of transverse vibration of the string is solved by solving the wave equation. One-dimensional wave equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

has a view. Here, a is the wave propagation speed. Based on the condition of the problem, let's also write the initial and boundary conditions:

$$u(0, t) = u(L, t) = 0, \quad \varphi(x) = x(x - L), \quad u_t(x, 0) = 0.$$

The NDSolve, Plot and Manipulate commands in the Wolfram Mathematica software package are used to solve this problem.

The NDSolve command is used to numerically solve differential equations. The plot command is used to draw the graph of the function. A function or a quantity can be manipulated using the Manipulate command.

Now let's go directly to the program for solving equation (1).

```
In[1]:= a = 0.1; L = 1; T = 10;
```

```
In[2]:= NDSolve[{D[u[x, t], {t, 2}] == a^2 * D[u[x, t], {x, 2}],
  u[x, 0] == x * (x - L), (D[u[x, t], t] /. t -> 0) == 0, u[0, t] == 0, u[L, t] == 0},
  u, {x, 0, L}, {t, 0, T}, PrecisionGoal -> 2]
```

```
Out[2]= {{u -> InterpolatingFunction[ Domain: {{0., 1.}, {0., 10.}} Output: scalar ]}}
```

It can be seen that initially constant quantities were declared, and NDSolve command was used to solve equation (1). To get more information about the solution of the equation, it is possible to visualize the solution for different moments of time by depicting it graphically (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The dependence of the function $u(x, 0)$ on the x coordinate.

By moving the slider in the upper left corner of Figure 1 to the right, it will be possible to observe the solution of equation (1) at different moments of time.

As can be seen from the graph, the obtained result corresponds to the initial and boundary conditions of the problem, i.e. both ends of the string are fixed and at

the initial moment of time, its appearance is a parabola of the form $\varphi(x) = x(x - L)$ have

The issue of heat dissipation

A rod whose length is equal to L is given. Its left end is kept at constant temperature u_1 . A constant heat flux q is given to the right end of the stern. Let the initial temperature distribution in the stern be like $\varphi(x)$. Solve the problem of heat dissipation in this stern?

Solving the problem of heat dissipation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = a^2 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

is solved by solving Eq. Let's write the initial and boundary conditions for equation (2) according to the condition of the problem:

$$u(0, t) = 0, \quad u(L, t) = \frac{q}{k}, \quad \varphi(x) = \frac{q \cdot x^2}{k \cdot L^3}$$

(2) The program for solving the equation looks like this:

```
In[1]:= a = 0.1; L = 1; T = 10; q = 0.01; k = 1;
```

```
In[2]:= NDSolve[{D[u[x, t], t] == a^2 * D[u[x, t], {x, 2}],
```

```
u[x, 0] ==  $\frac{q * x^3}{k * L^3}$ , u[0, t] == 0, u[L, t] ==  $\frac{q}{k}$ }, u, {x, 0, L}, {t, 0, T}]
```

```
Out[2]= {{u -> InterpolatingFunction[ Domain: {{0., 1.}, {0., 10.}} Output: scalar ]}}
```

When solving equations of this type, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the initial and boundary conditions must be correctly selected for the correct operation of the program!

The solution of the resulting equation (2) can also be observed at different moments of time (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. a) dependence of $u(x, 0)$ on x coordinate, b) x of $u(x, 7)$ depending on the coordinate.

Laplace equation

Find the solution of Laplace's equation $\Delta u = 0$ inside the rectangle $0 \leq x \leq a, 0 \leq y \leq b$? $u(x, y)$ takes the following values within the boundaries of this quadrilateral:

$$u(0, y) = A \cdot \sin \frac{\pi y}{b}, u(a, y) = 0, u(x, 0) = B \cdot \sin \frac{\pi x}{a}, u(x, b) = 0.$$

As can be seen from the condition of the problem, it is necessary to solve the Laplace equation for the two-dimensional case. So, the Laplace operator in two dimension will be like and to us

$$\Delta u = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

the equation is required to be solved for the boundary conditions of the problem.

Now let's go to the program for solving equation (3):

```
In[1]:= a = 1; b = 2;
```

```
Tenglama = Laplacian[u[x, y], {x, y}] == 0;
```

```
Ω = Rectangle[{0, 0}, {a, b}];
```

```
In[4]:= Yechim = NDSolveValue[{Tenglama, u[0, y] == Sin[π * y/b],
```

```
u[a, y] == 0, u[x, 0] == Sin[π * x/a], u[x, b] == 0}, u[x, y], {x, y} ∈ Ω]
```

```
Out[4]:= InterpolatingFunction[  

 Domain: {{0., 1.}, {0., 2.}}  

  Output scalar  

  ] [x, y]
```

Here, too, similar to the above problems, initially unchanged quantities were announced. Then you can see that the area (rectangle) where the solution needs to be searched is included in the program. Unlike the previous problems, the Plot3D command is used to graphically represent the solution. Because the solution $u(x, y)$ sought in the Laplace equation is a function of two variables. Therefore, it is necessary to depict the solution graphically in three-dimensional space (Fig. 3).

```
In[5]= Plot3D[Yechim // Evaluate, {x, y} ∈ Ω, PlotRange → All, PlotTheme → "Business"]
```


Figure 3. Dependence of $u(x, y)$ on x and y coordinates.

CONCLUSION

Using the "Wolfram mathematica" program, mathematical physics problems were modeled on the computer. The obtained results were checked for compliance with the initial and boundary conditions of the problems. It is possible to adapt the developed programs for various initial and boundary conditions based on the conditions of the problem. The advantage of such programs is that by visualizing the solution of the equation for different moments of time, you can get more detailed information about the observed process.

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